

33 **1. Introduction**

34 Proximity search is successfully used to retrieve data objects that are close
35 to a given query object under some metric function. It has a vast number of
36 applications in many branches of computer science, including pattern recogni-
37 tion, computational biology, and multimedia information retrieval, to name but
38 a few. This search paradigm, referred to as *metric search*, is based on the as-
39 sumption that data objects are represented as elements of a metric space (D, d)
40 where the *metric*¹ function $d : D \times D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ provides a measure of the closeness
41 of the data objects.

42 In metric search, the main concern is processing and structuring a finite set
43 of data $X \subset D$ so that *proximity queries* can be answered quickly and with a low
44 computational cost. A proximity query is defined by a query object $q \in D$ and
45 a proximity condition, such as “find all the objects within a threshold distance
46 of q ” (*range query*) or “finding the k closest objects to q ” (*k-nearest neighbour*
47 *query*). The response to a query is the set of all the objects $o \in X$ that satisfy
48 the considered proximity condition. In this work, we focus on the k -nearest
49 neighbour (k -NN) search since, as also highlighted in [2, 3], (i) it allows us to
50 control the size of the results set, and (ii) it is simpler to use in high-dimensional
51 space where it is not obvious to define a meaningful distance value to be used
52 with other search paradigms, like the range query. However, providing an exact
53 response to a k -NN query is not feasible if the search space is very large or it
54 has a high intrinsic dimensionality since it would be necessary to inspect a large
55 fraction of the data to process the query. In such cases, the exact search rarely
56 outperforms a sequential scan [4, 5]. To overcome this phenomenon, known
57 as *curse of dimensionality* [6], researchers proposed several *approximate search*
58 methods that are less (but still) affected by it. The main idea of approximate
59 methods is to efficiently find a set of results that is likely to contain most of the
60 objects that satisfy the query proximity condition. However, the efficiency of
61 these methods comes at the expense of a certain reduction of the accuracy (e.g.
62 false hits or missing results). A limited imprecision in the response to the query,
63 however, is totally tolerated in many applications, such as multimedia retrieval
64 where the concept of “(di)similarity” may differ on the user’s expectations, and
65 close approximations may be good enough for human perception [7].

66 Many Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) methods are based on the idea
67 of mapping the data objects into a more tractable space in which we can ef-
68 ficiently perform the search. Successful examples are the *Permutation-Based*
69 *Indexing* (PBI) approaches that represent data objects as a sequence of iden-
70 tifiers (*permutation*). Typically, the permutation for an object o is computed
71 as a ranking list of some preselected reference points (*pivots*) according to their
72 distance to o . The main rationale behind this approach is that if two objects are
73 very close one to the other they will sort the set of pivots in a very similar way,

¹Throughout this paper, we use the terms “metric” and “distance” interchangeably to indicate a function satisfying the metric postulates of non-negativity, identity, symmetry, and triangle inequality [1].

74 and thus the corresponding permutation representations will be close as well.
75 The search in the permutation space is used to select a candidate result set that
76 is then typically refined by comparing each candidate object to the query one
77 (according to the actual metric governing the data space). This refinement step,
78 therefore, requires access to the original data, which is likely to be too large to
79 fit into the main memory. However, some kind of refinement step is likely to
80 be necessary as the search in the permutation space usually has relatively low
81 precision.

82 In this paper, we focus on permutation-based k -NN search and we inves-
83 tigate several approaches to perform the refining step without access to the
84 original data. Our techniques approximate the actual distance between a query
85 and the candidate objects by exploiting the distances between the objects and
86 the pivots (calculated at indexing time and stored within the permutations)
87 and the distances between the query and the pivots (evaluated when computing
88 the query permutation). In particular, for a large class of metric spaces that
89 meet the so-called “ n -point property” [8, 9] we propose the use of the *nSimplex*
90 *projection* [10] that allows mapping metric objects into a finite-dimensional Eu-
91 clidean space where upper- and lower- bounds for the original distances can be
92 calculated. We show how these distance bounds can be used to improve the
93 permutation-based results without accessing to the original data set.

94 A preliminary version of this work appeared in [11]. The present contri-
95 bution gives, also, a more detailed description of the proposed approaches and
96 an extensive experimental evaluation. In particular, it includes new results on
97 large scale and investigates the use of compressed versions of the inverted files
98 to index the data. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2
99 reviews related work. Section 3 provides basic concepts of the metric space
100 transformations used in our work (namely, permutation-based representations,
101 Pivoted embedding, and *nSimplex* projection). In Section 4 we describe several
102 pivot-based approaches to refine a permutation-based candidate set. A detailed
103 experimental evaluation and analysis of those approaches is presented in Section
104 5. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in the last section.

105 Table 1 summarises the notation used in this paper.

106 2. Related Work

107 The idea of approximating the distance between any two metric objects by
108 comparing their permutation-based representations was originally proposed in
109 [12, 13]. Several techniques for indexing and searching permutations were con-
110 sidered in literature, including indexes based on inverted files, like the *Metric*
111 *Inverted File* (MI-File) [14] and its variants [15], or using prefix trees, like the
112 *Permutation Prefix Index* (PP-Index) [2] and the *Pivot Permutation Prefix In-*
113 *dex* (PPP-Index) [16]. In [17], the metric objects in the inverted index are
114 represented by a signature built from the l nearest references to them. How-
115 ever, in all above approaches, the candidate result set identified by performing
116 the search in the permutation space should be refined to achieve high effective-
117 ness. Typically the results are refining by directly comparing the query object

Table 1: Notation used throughout this paper

Symbol	Definition
(D, d)	metric space
X	finite search space, $X \subseteq D$
$\mathcal{P}_n = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$	set of pivots, $p_i \in D$
n	number of pivots
o, s	data objects, $o, s \in X$
q	query, $q \in D$
k, k'	number of results of a nearest neighbour search
amp	amplification factor
Π_o	pivot permutation
Π_o^{-1}	inverted permutation
l	permutation prefix length (location parameter)
$\Pi_{o,l}$	permutation prefix of length l (truncated permutation)
$\Pi_{o,l}^{-1}$	inverted truncated permutation
$PivotSet(\Pi_{o,l})$	the pivots whose identifiers appear in $\Pi_{o,l}$
$\Gamma_{o,q}$	pivots in the intersection $PivotSet(\Pi_{q,l}) \cap PivotSet(\Pi_{o,l})$
$S_{\rho,l}$	Spearman's rho with location parameter l
ℓ_2	Euclidean distance
ℓ_∞	Chebyshev distance
$f_{\mathcal{P}_n} : (D, d) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \ell_\infty)$	Pivoted embedding
$\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n} : (D, d) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \ell_2)$	nSimplex projection
$ \cdot $	size of a set

118 with the obtained candidate results according to the original distance and data
119 representation.

120 The common approach to generate a permutation-based representation of
121 a data object is ordering the identifiers of a set of pivots according to their
122 distances to the object [18]. However, the computation of these distances is just
123 one, yet effective, approach to associate a permutation to each data object. For
124 example, the *Deep Permutations* [19] have been recently proposed as an efficient
125 and effective alternative for generating permutations of emerging deep features.
126 However, this approach is suitable only for specific data domains while the
127 traditional approach is generally applicable since it requires only the existence
128 of a distance function to compare data objects.

129 In [20], Figueroa et al. have tried different distances between permutations
130 instead of the canonical Spearman Footrule or Spearman Rho metrics. The aim
131 of this work, however, was to reduce the number of distance computations and
132 the size of the index.

133 The distances between the data objects and a set of pivots can be used also
134 to embed the data into another metric space where it is possible to deduce
135 upper- and lower- bounds on the actual distance of any pair of objects. In this
136 context, one of the very first embeddings proposed in a metric search scenario
137 was the one representing each data object with a vector of its distances to the
138 pivots. The LAESA [21] is a notable example of indexing technique using this
139 approach. Connor et al. [10, 9, 22] observed that for a large class of metric
140 spaces it is possible to use the distances to a set of n pivots to project the data
141 objects into a n -dimensional Euclidean space such that in the projected space
142 1) the distances object-pivots are preserved, 2) the Euclidean distance between
143 any two points is a lower-bound of the actual distance, 3) also an upper-bound
144 can be easily computed. They called this approach *nSimplex projection* and
145 they proved that it can be used in all the metric spaces meeting the *n-point*
146 *property* [23]. As also pointed out in [8], many common metric spaces meet the
147 desired property, like Cartesian spaces of any dimension with the Euclidean,
148 cosine or quadratic form distances, probability spaces with the Jensen-Shannon
149 or the Triangular distance, and more generally any Hilbert-embeddable space
150 [23, 24].

151 Recently, The nSimplex projection has been exploited to generate a novel
152 permutation-based representation for metric objects, called SPLX-Perm [?]. It
153 is based on the idea of mapping the data object to Euclidean vectors, which are
154 in turn transformed into permutations using an approach similar to that used
155 in the Deep Permutations [19].

156 3. Background

157 This section summarises key concepts of some metric space transformations
158 based on the use of distances between data objects and a set of pivots. The
159 rationale behind these approaches is to project the original data into a space that
160 has better indexing properties than the original one, or where the function used
161 to compare the objects is less expensive than the original distance. In particular,

162 we review data transformations into permutation spaces (where objects can be
 163 efficiently indexed using PBI methods) and two pivot-based embeddings that
 164 allow computing upper- and lower- bounds of the actual distance.

165 3.1. Permutation-Based Representations

166 Let \mathcal{D} a data domain and $d : \mathcal{D} \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ a *metric* function on it². A
 167 permutation-based representation Π_o (briefly *permutation*) of an object $o \in \mathcal{D}$
 168 with respect to a fixed set of *pivots*, $\{p_1, \dots, p_n\} \subset \mathcal{D}$, is the sequence of pivots
 169 identifiers ordered by their distance to o .

Formally, the permutation $\Pi_o = [\Pi_o(1), \Pi_o(2), \dots, \Pi_o(n)]$ lists the pivot identifiers $\{1, \dots, n\}$ in an order such that $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$,

$$d(o, p_{\Pi_o(i)}) < d(o, p_{\Pi_o(i+1)}) \quad (1)$$

or

$$[d(o, p_{\Pi_o(i)}) = d(o, p_{\Pi_o(i+1)})] \wedge [\Pi_o(i) < \Pi_o(i+1)]. \quad (2)$$

170 An equivalent permutation-based representation is the *inverted permutation*,
 171 defined as $\Pi_o^{-1} = [\Pi_o^{-1}(1), \Pi_o^{-1}(2), \dots, \Pi_o^{-1}(n)]$, where $\Pi_o^{-1}(i)$ denotes the position
 172 of a pivot p_i in the permutation Π_o . The inverted permutation is such that
 173 $\Pi_o(\Pi_o^{-1}(i)) = i$. Note that the value at the coordinate i in the permutation
 174 Π_o is the identifier of the pivot at i -th position in the ranked list of the nearest
 175 pivots to o ; the value at the coordinate i in the inverted representation Π_o^{-1} is
 176 the rank of the pivot p_i in the list of the nearest pivots to o .

177 The inverted permutation representation is often used in practice since it
 178 allows us to represent permutations in a Cartesian coordinate system and easily
 179 compute most of the commonly-used distances between permutations as distances
 180 between Cartesian points. Several metric functions have been used in
 181 literature to compare permutations, notably including Kendall’s tau, Spearman’s
 182 Rho and the Spearman’s Footrule distances. In this paper, we use the
 183 Spearman’s Rho. It is defined as $S_\rho(\Pi_o, \Pi_s) = \ell_2(\Pi_o^{-1}, \Pi_s^{-1})$ for any two per-
 184 mutations Π_o, Π_s .

Most of the PBI methods, e.g. [14, 2, 16], use only a fixed-length prefix of the permutations to represent and compare objects. This choice is based on the intuition that the most relevant information in the permutation is present in its very first elements, i.e. the identifiers of the closest pivots. Moreover, using the positions of the nearest l out of n pivots often leads to obtaining better or similar effectiveness than using the full-length permutation [14, 18], resulting also in a more compact data encoding. The permutation prefixes are compared using *top- l distances* [25]. An example is given by the Spearman’s Rho with location parameter l , which is defined as $S_{\rho,l}(\Pi_o, \Pi_s) = \ell_2(\Pi_{o,l}^{-1}, \Pi_{s,l}^{-1})$, where

²In this work, we focus on metric search. The requirement that the function d satisfies the metric postulates is sufficient, but not necessary, to produce a permutation-based representation. For example, d may be a dissimilarity function.

$\Pi_{o,l}^{-1}$ is the *inverted truncated permutation*:

$$\Pi_{o,l}^{-1}(i) = \begin{cases} \Pi_o^{-1}(i) & \text{if } \Pi_o^{-1}(i) \leq l \\ l + 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

185 3.2. Pivoted embedding

The distances between the metric objects and a set of pivots $\mathcal{P}_n = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ can be used to embed a metric space into $(\mathbb{R}^n, \ell_\infty)$ by using the following transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\mathcal{P}_n} : (D, d) &\rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \ell_\infty) \\ o &\rightarrow [d(o, p_1), \dots, d(o, p_n)] \end{aligned}$$

The triangle inequality of the metric governing the space guarantees that

$$\max_{i=1, \dots, n} |d(o, p_i) - d(s, p_i)| \leq d(o, s) \leq \min_{i=1, \dots, n} |d(o, p_i) + d(s, p_i)| \quad (4)$$

186 which it means that $\ell_\infty(f_{\mathcal{P}_n}(o), f_{\mathcal{P}_n}(s))$ is a lower-bound of $d(o, s)$ and that also
 187 an upper-bound can be defined using the projected objects $f_{\mathcal{P}_n}(o), f_{\mathcal{P}_n}(s)$ (see
 188 [1, pp.28]). Please note that if we use just a subset \mathcal{P}_l of size l of the pivots
 189 $\{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$, the corresponding mapping $f_{\mathcal{P}_l}$ provides upper- and lower- bounds
 190 that are less tight than that obtained using $f_{\mathcal{P}_n}$.

191 This family of embeddings, referred to as *Pivoted embedding* in the following,
 192 are typically used in indexing tables like LAESA [21] or for space pruning [1].
 193 However, as further described in Section 4, in this work we used them not
 194 for indexing purpose, but rather as techniques to approximate the distances
 195 between a query and data objects already indexed using a permutation-based
 196 approach.

197 3.3. *nSimplex projection*

The *nSimplex projection* [10] is a space transformation of the form

$$\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n} : (D, d) \rightarrow (\mathbb{R}^n, \ell_2)$$

198 that uses the distances to a set of pivots $\mathcal{P}_n = \{p_1, \dots, p_n\}$ for embedding
 199 metric objects into a finite-dimensional Euclidean space. It can be applied to
 200 any metric space that meets the so called *n-point property* [23], which provides
 201 geometric guarantees stronger than triangle inequality. In particular, a metric
 202 space has the *n-point property* if, and only if, any set of n points of the space
 203 can be *isometrically* embedded into a $(n - 1)$ -dimensional Euclidean space, i.e.
 204 there exist a mapping of those points to n Euclidean vectors that preserves all
 205 the $\binom{n}{2}$ inter-points distances. In other words, the n points can be isometrically
 206 mapped to the vertices of a $(n - 1)$ -dimensional simplex³.

³A simplex is a generalisation of a triangle (2-dimensional simplex) or a tetrahedron (3-dimensional simplex) in arbitrary dimensions. Specifically, the $(n - 1)$ -dimensional simplex generated by the vertices v_1, \dots, v_n equals the union of all the line segments joining v_n to the points of the $(n - 2)$ -dimensional simplex of vertices v_1, \dots, v_{n-1} .

The n -point property guarantees that given the set of pivots \mathcal{P}_n , we can determine the vectors v_{p_1}, \dots, v_{p_n} such that

$$\forall i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : \ell_2(v_{p_i}, v_{p_j}) = d(p_i, p_j).$$

We refer the $(n - 1)$ -dimensional simplex generated by those vectors to as the *simplex base*. Then, for any further object $o \in D$ the $(n + 1)$ -point property guarantees that there exists a vertex $v_o \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} : \ell_2(v_{p_i}, v_o) = d(p_i, o),$$

207 i.e., the vector v_o is the apex of a n -dimensional simplex built upon the simplex
 208 base where the length of the i -th edge connecting v_o to the simplex base equals
 209 the actual distance $d(p_i, o)$. The nSimplex projection $\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}$ is the transformation
 210 that maps an object $o \in D$ to the apex $v_o \in \mathbb{R}^n$ built upon the simplex base.
 211 Connor et al. [10] provided an iterative algorithm to compute the coordinates
 212 of the vertices v_{p_i} of the simplex base as well as the coordinates of the apex
 213 v_o associated to a metric object o . Remark that this algorithm determines
 214 those coordinates by only exploiting the distances $d(p_i, p_j)$ and $d(p_i, o)$, for
 215 $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Moreover, the simplex base is computed once and is reused for
 216 projecting every data object. Given the distances $d(p_i, o)$, the cost for computing
 217 v_o is $O(n)$ Euclidean distance between vectors having less than n dimensions.

One of the main outcomes of this embedding is that it allows us to determine upper- and lower-bounds of the actual distance by computing the Euclidean distance between two vectors. In facts, given the apexes

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}(o) &= [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n] \\ \phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}(s) &= [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-1}, y_n] \end{aligned}$$

it holds

$$\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \leq d(o, s) \leq \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (x_i - y_i)^2 + (x_n + y_n)^2} \quad (5)$$

for any two objects $o, s \in D$. Therefore given the vector

$$\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}^-(s) = [y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-1}, -y_n]$$

218 we have that $\ell_2(\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}(o), \phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}(s))$ and $\ell_2(\phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}(o), \phi_{\mathcal{P}_n}^-(s))$ are respectively a lower-
 219 and upper-bound for $d(o, s)$. Moreover, these bounds become tighter with
 220 increasing number of pivots n [26, 10]. Recently,

221 Note that, as observed in [8, 10], there exist a large class of metric spaces
 222 that satisfy the n -point property and therefore can be transformed by the nSimplex
 223 projection. Examples are given by the Euclidean spaces of any dimension,
 224 spaces with the Triangular or Jensen-Shannon distances, and, more generally,
 225 any Hilbert-embeddable spaces. Moreover, if a metric space does not meet the
 226 n -point property, (e.g. Hamming or Chebyshev metrics), there always exists a
 227 proximity preserving mapping of this space into a metric space with this prop-
 228 erty [27].

Figure 1: Illustration of the pipeline adopted in this work to compute the approximate k -NN results to a query by re-ranking a permutation-based candidate result set.

229 4. Re-ranking Permutation-Based Candidate Set

230 The permutation-based methods for approximate search are filter-and-refine
 231 approaches that map original data (D, d) into a permutation space. The per-
 232 mutation representations are used to identify a set of candidate results for a
 233 given query $q \in D$. The candidate results are then refined, typically by compar-
 234 ing the candidate objects with the query one according to the actual distance
 235 d . This refining approach based on the actual distance, however, requires to
 236 store the original data set and access to it at query time. In the following,
 237 we investigate the use of other refining approaches. The aim is improving the
 238 permutation-based results while getting rid of the original data set.

239 We focus on the k -NN search and we assume that the data objects are
 240 represented and indexed using permutation prefixes instead of the full-length
 241 permutations (as done in many PBI approach [2, 14, 16]). Let $CandSet(q)$,
 242 with $|CandSet(q)| = k' > k$, the set of candidate results selected using the
 243 permutation-based encoding. The candidate result set can be built, for example,
 244 by performing a k' -NN search in the permutation space (e.g. using the MI-File
 245 [14]) or by finding objects with a common permutation prefix (e.g. using the
 246 PP-codes [2]). The candidate result set is then refined by selecting the top- k
 247 candidate objects ranked according to a dissimilarity function (Figure 1). To
 248 use a dissimilarity function that does not require to access to the original data,
 249 we propose to re-rank the objects based of their distances to a set of pivots.
 250 In facts, the distances between the objects and the pivots are calculated when
 251 computing the permutation-based representation and therefore can be easily
 252 reused at query time.

253 Let $PivotSet(\Pi_{o, l})$ the set of the l closest pivots to the object o , i.e. the
 254 pivots whose identifiers appear in the prefix permutation $\Pi_{o, l}$. We assume that
 255 the distances between each object and its l closest pivots are stored and indexed
 256 within the object permutation prefix. This can be done with a slight modifi-
 257 cation of the used permutation-based index. Figure 2 shows a naive example
 258 for integrating the object-pivot distances into the posting lists, such as the ones
 259 used in the MI-file [14]. In the following, we assume that the objects are indexed

Figure 2: Example of traditional posting lists and posting lists with distances generated to index three objects using five pivots and a prefix length $l = 3$

260 using this modified version of inverted files, however, the approaches presented
 261 in this paper can be extended to cope with different permutation-based indexes.

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We propose to refine the candidate result set according to a dissimilarity function derived from the distance bounds provided either by the *Pivoted embedding* (Sec. 3.2) and the *nSimplex projection* (Sec. 3.3), since these metric mappings rely only on the object-pivot distances. Specifically, at query time, for each object $o \in \text{CandSet}(q)$ we approximate the actual distance $d(o, q)$ on the basis of the distances $d(o, p_j)$, $d(q, p_j)$ for $p_j \in \Gamma_{o, q} = \text{PivotSet}(\Pi_{q, l}) \cap \text{PivotSet}(\Pi_{o, l})$ as follows:

Pivoted embedding - As a consequence of Equation 4 we have

$$\max_{p_j \in \Gamma_{o, q}} |d(o, p_j) - d(q, p_j)| \leq d(o, q) \leq \min_{p_j \in \Gamma_{o, q}} |d(o, p_j) + d(q, p_j)| \quad (6)$$

so we consider three possible re-rankings of the candidate objects, based on the following dissimilarity measures

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{lwb}(o, q) &= \max_{p_j \in \Gamma_{o, q}} |d(o, p_j) - d(q, p_j)| && \text{lower-bound} \\
 P_{upb}(o, q) &= \min_{p_j \in \Gamma_{o, q}} (d(o, p_j) + d(q, p_j)) && \text{upper-bound} \\
 P_{mean}(o, q) &= (P_{upb}(o, q) + P_{lwb}(o, q))/2 && \text{mean}
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplex projection - For each candidate object o , the pivots in $\Gamma_{o, q}$ are used to build the simplex base. The simplex base and the distances $d(o, p_j)$,

$d(q, p_j)$ with $p_j \in \Gamma_{o,q}$ are used to compute the apexes $\phi_{\Gamma_{o,q}}(o), \phi_{\Gamma_{o,q}}(q), \phi_{\Gamma_{o,q}}^-(q) \in \mathbb{R}^h$, where $h = |\Gamma_{o,q}| \leq l$. We consider the re-rankings of the candidate objects based on the following dissimilarity measures:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{lwb}(o, q) &= \ell_2(\phi_h(o), \phi_h(q)) && \text{lower-bound} \\ S_{upb}(o, q) &= \ell_2(\phi_h(o), \phi_h^-(q)) && \text{upper-bound} \\ S_{mean}(o, q) &= (S_{upb}(o, q) + S_{lwb}(o, q))/2 && \text{mean} \end{aligned}$$

Other dissimilarity functions over the apex vectors may be considered as well, in particular, any function that is always between the lower-bound and the upper-bound could be a good option since both the Simplex bounds asymptotically approach the true distance when increasing the number of pivots. In this work, we also consider the Zenith function, which was recently proposed in [28], that equals the quadratic mean of the lower- and upper-bounds

$$S_{zenith}(o, q) = \sqrt{(S_{upb}(o, q)^2 + S_{lwb}(o, q)^2) / 2} \quad \text{zenith}$$

270 The main difference between the mean and zenith distance is that the
271 latter has a geometrical interpretation as the Euclidean distance between
272 two vertex in \mathbb{R}^{h+1} (see [28] for futher details).

Note that the Simplex bounds are highly affected by the number h of pivots used to build the simplex base (the higher h , the tighter the bounds), moreover the number h and the used simplex base change when changing the candidate object o . This means that the quality of the simplex-based approximation of the distance $d(o, q)$ may vary significantly when changing the considered candidate object. To overcome this issue, we also considered the re-ranking according to

$$\begin{aligned} S_{norm.mean}(o, q) &= S_{mean}(o, q)/g(h) && \text{normalized mean} \\ S_{norm.zenith}(o, q) &= S_{zenith}(o, q)/g(h) && \text{normalized zenith} \end{aligned}$$

273 where $g(h)$ is a normalization factor, further discussed in Section 5.3.

274 The lower-bounds S_{lwb} and P_{lwb} are metrics, while the other considered mea-
275 sures are dissimilarity functions. Finally, we remark that for all these approaches
276 no new object-pivot distance is evaluated at either indexing or query time, since
277 the used distances are already computed for building the permutation-based rep-
278 resentations of the objects/query. Moreover, the distances $d(o, p_j)$ with $p_j \in \Gamma_{o,q}$
279 are retrieved while scanning the posting list to build the candidate result set,
280 therefore the considered re-ranking approaches do not require further disk ac-
281 cesses in addition to the index accesses already made to find the candidate
282 results.

283 5. Experiments

284 In this section, we experimentally evaluate the quality of the re-ranking
285 approaches discussed above. We first describe the employed data sets (Section
286 5.1) and other experimental settings (Section 5.2). Then, we report results and
287 their analysis for several case studies (Sections 5.3-5.5)

288 5.1. Test Data

289 The experiments were conducted on three publicly available data sets, namely
290 YFCC100M [29], Twitter-Glove [30], and SISAP Colors [31]. To test our tech-
291 niques on a variety of metric spaces, we selected a different type of data descrip-
292 tor and metric for each data set:

293 **YFCC100M** is a collection that contains about 96M images, all uploaded to
294 Flickr between 2004 and 2014 and published under a CC commercial or
295 non-commercial license. As image descriptors we used deep Convolutional
296 Neural Network features obtained from the activations of the *fc6* layer
297 of the HybridNet [32] after the ReLu and the ℓ_2 normalization stages.
298 The resulting features are 4,096-dimensional vectors. These feature were
299 originally extracted by Amato et al. [33] and are available at [http://](http://www.deepfeatures.org/)
300 www.deepfeatures.org/. We followed the common choice of using the
301 *Euclidean distance* for comparing this kind of features.

302 **Twitter-GloVe** is a collection of 1.2M GloVe [30] features (word embeddings)
303 trained on tweets. We used the 100-dimensional pre-trained word vectors
304 available at <https://nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/>. These word
305 vectors are often used as vocabulary terms to embed a document into a
306 vector representation, for example by averaging the vectors of the terms
307 contained in the text. In such cases, the space of the vocabulary terms is
308 representative of the space of the document embeddings. The Euclidean
309 distance or the Cosine similarity are typically used to compare two GloVe
310 vectors since they provide an effective method for measuring the linguistic
311 or semantic similarity of the corresponding words. In our experiments we
312 used the *Cosine distance*, defined as $d_{\text{Cos}}(x, y) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{x \cdot y}{\|x\|_2 \|y\|_2}}$, which
313 is equivalent to the Cosine similarity (i.e., the closest object to a query
314 according to d_{Cos} are the most similar objects to the query according to
315 the Cosine similarity).

SISAP Colors is a commonly used benchmark for metric indexing approaches.
It contains about 113K feature vectors of dimensions 112, representing
color histograms of medical images. We compare the feature vectors using
the *Jensen-Shannon distance*, which is defined as the square root of the
Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSDiv), i.e. $d_{\text{JS}}(x, y) = \sqrt{\text{JSDiv}(x, y)}$. The
term Jensen-Shannon divergence is used variously with slightly different
meanings in literature; to avoid ambiguity, we follow the definition used

(a) *YFCC100M* (*IDim*= 276) (b) *Twitter-GloVe* (*IDim*= 106) (c) *SISAP Colors* (*IDim*= 8)

Figure 3: Probability density function estimated on a sample of 500,000 distances.

in [8]:

$$JSDiv(x, y) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_i h(x_i) + h(y_i) - h(x_i + y_i),$$

where $h(z) = -z \log_2 z$.

The distance distributions of the three considered data sets are depicted in Figure 3. In the figure captions we also report the Intrinsic Dimensionality (*IDim*) of the data that was estimated as in [34], i.e. $IDim = \frac{\mu^2}{\sigma^2}$, where μ is the mean and σ is the standard deviation of the distances between the data objects.

5.2. Experimental setup

For each data set we build a ground-truth for the exact k -NN search related to 1,000 randomly-selected queries.⁴ The ground-truths are used to evaluate the quality of the approximate results obtained by re-ranking a permutation-based result set of size $k' \geq k$. Specifically, for each query object we select a candidate result set by performing a k' -NN search in the permutation space. Then we re-rank the candidate results and we select the top- k objects as the approximate answer to the k -NN query.

The quality of the approximate results was evaluated using the $recall@k$, defined as $|\mathcal{R} \cap \mathcal{R}^A|/k$, where \mathcal{R} is the result set of the exact k -NN search in the original metric space and \mathcal{R}^A is the approximate result set. We set $k = 10$ and $k' = 100$, thus the candidate result set is computed by performing a 100-NN search in the permutation space.

The permutation-based representations of the data objects were generated using a total of $n = 4,000$ pivots for YFCC100M and Twitter-GloVe data, and

⁴The query objects were removed from the ground-truths of Twitter GloVe and SISAP Color data sets. For the YFCC100M we keep the query objects in the ground-truth to have results comparable with other research papers that used the same ground-truth (e.g. [19, 11]). Please also note that many re-ranking measures tested in this paper are not metrics, thus there are no guarantees that the less similar object to a query will be the query itself.

336 $n = 1,000$ pivots for the smaller SISAP Colors data set. In our tests, we used
 337 fixed-length permutation prefixes to represent the data objects. The permu-
 338 tation prefixes were compared using *Spearman’s rho with location parameter*
 339 metric, where the location parameter is the length l of the permutation pre-
 340 fixes. Note that the case $l = n$ simply corresponds to use of the full-length
 341 permutations with the traditional Spearman’s rho metric. In the experiments,
 342 we evaluate the performance for various permutation prefix lengths.

343 5.3. Results

344 This section presents comparative results for all the approaches described
 345 in Sec. 4 to re-rank a permutation-based candidate results set. We remind the
 346 reader that the considered techniques are based on various **Pivoted embedding**
 347 and **Simplex projection** dissimilarity measures (namely, lower-bound, upper-
 348 bound, and mean), as well as the **Simplex** zenith function. We compared these
 349 approaches also with two baselines: 1) the permutation-based results before any
 350 re-ranking, 2) the re-ranking based on the actual distance. The permutation-
 351 based results before any re-ranking are simply the first k candidate objects
 352 ordered according to their permutation-based distance to the query (i.e. the k -
 353 NN results in the permutation space). A good re-ranking technique in terms of
 354 effectiveness should at least improve the recall of the permutation-based results,
 355 and ideally achieves a performance close to that obtained using the re-ranking
 356 based on the actual distance. In fact, the latter one is the approach that provides
 357 the maximum possible recall for the given candidate result set, but it requires
 358 to access the original metric object o to compute the distance $d(q, o)$ between
 359 the query q and every candidate object o .

360 Figure 4 illustrates the results on Twitter-GloVe and SISAP Colors data sets.
 361 Figures 5a and 5b show the results on two subsets of YFCC100M that contain
 362 1M and 10M images, respectively. We used the term “Perms” to indicate the
 363 permutation-based results before any re-ranking, and “Perms, re-rank(f)” for
 364 the re-ranking based on the measure f , where f may be either the

- 365 • actual distance d ,
- 366 • **Pivoted embedding** measures ($P_{lwb}, P_{upb}, P_{mean}$),
- 367 • **Simplex** measures ($S_{lwb}, S_{upb}, S_{mean}, S_{zenith}, S_{norm.mean}, S_{norm.zenith}$).

368 In each graph, we report the *recall@10* varying the length l of the permutation
 369 prefixes used to represent the data objects (the number n of pivots is fixed).
 370 Please note that the prefix length l influences the quality of the candidate set
 371 to be re-ranked, as well as the quality of the **Pivoted embedding** and **Simplex**
 372 **projection** distance approximations. In fact, for a fixed value l and for a candi-
 373 date object o , the number h of pivots used to compute the distance approxi-
 374 mations is less than l ; moreover, it varies and depends on the candidate object
 375 o as it is equal to the cardinality of $\Gamma_{o,q}$ (i.e. the intersection between the query
 376 permutation prefix and the object permutation prefix). Typically h is greater
 377 for objects in top positions in the permutation-based result list and decrease for

(a) Twitter-GloVe, Cosine distance, $n = 4,000$

(b) SISAP Colors, Jensen-Shannon distance, $n = 1,000$

Figure 4: *Recall@10* of several re-ranking approaches varying the permutation prefix length l . The candidate set to be reordered is selected with a 100-NN search in the permutation space using the Spearman's rho with location parameter l .

(a) Results on 1 million images

(b) Results on 10 million images.

Figure 5: YFCC100M, Euclidean distance: $Recall@10$ varying the permutation prefix length l on subsets of 1M images (5a) and 10M images (5b). The number of pivots is fixed to $n = 4,000$. The candidate set to be reordered is selected with a 100-NN search in the permutation space using the Spearman's rho with location parameter l .

Figure 6: YFCC100M, Euclidean Distance - Average relative error of the **Pivoted embedding** and **Simplex embedding** bounds with respect to the actual distance varying the number of h of pivots used to compute the bounds. Similar trends are obtained on Twitter-GloVe and SISAP colors data sets.

378 objects that are far according to the permutation-based distance. Moreover, the
 379 greater the l , the greater the h and so the better the approximation bounds.

380 Surprisingly, we observed that in almost all the tested cases the **Pivoted**
 381 **embedding** approach greatly degrades the quality of the permutation-based re-
 382 sults. Moreover, on YFCC100M and Twitter-GloVe it never reaches a *recall@10*
 383 greater than 0.3. Hence, the **Pivoted** distance approximations resulted to be
 384 not adequate for the considered re-ranking purpose. One of the reasons for its
 385 poor performance is that the **Pivoted** lower-bound approximates well the actual
 386 distance $d(o, q)$ only if o and q are very close to each other in the original metric
 387 space, or if $\Gamma_{o,q}$ contains at least one pivot that is very close to q and far to o (or
 388 vice versa). However, for randomly selected pivots in high dimensional space
 389 this is unlikely to happen: for a random pivot p and for an object o not so close
 390 to q , we often have that the distances $d(o, p)$ and $d(q, p)$ are both close to the
 391 mean value in the distribution of the data distances, and so the lower-bound
 392 results to be close to zero. This means that when we use the **Pivoted** lower-
 393 bound for re-ranking purpose, it may happen that many objects are incorrectly
 394 swapped and far objects can be assigned in top-positions. In addition, we ob-
 395 served that the **Pivoted** distance bounds have high relative errors with respect
 396 to the actual distance and that these errors slightly decrease when increasing
 397 the number h of pivots used to compute the bounds (Figure 6a).

398 The **Simplex** distance bounds showed similar drawbacks when using rela-
 399 tively small prefix lengths. In particular, they are mostly influenced by the
 400 fact that the **Simplex** bounds asymptotically approach the true distances when
 401 increasing the number h of pivots used to build the simplex base and that the
 402 tightness of the bounds highly depends on h . In fact, in all the tested cases, we
 403 observed that there exists a value \tilde{h} for which the full convergence is achieved.
 404 This value is 4,096 for YFCC100M, and about 100 for Twitter-GloVe/SISAP
 405 Colors. The effect of the convergence of the **Simplex** bounds is evident in both

406 the Twitter-GloVe (Figure 4a) and the SISAP Colors (Figure 4b) data: for
 407 $l > 300$ we observed that the number of pivots in the intersection $\Gamma_{o,q}$ starts
 408 to exceed $\tilde{h} = 100$ for most of the candidate objects o , and so all the **Simplex**
 409 bounds provide an exact or almost exact approximation of the actual distances.
 410 As a consequence, for $l > 300$ all the recall curves of the **Simplex**-based re-
 411 ranking approaches coincide with the recall curve obtained using the re-ranking
 412 based on the actual distance. For the YFC100M data set, instead, the **Simplex**
 413 bounds recall curves do not reach the values obtained by using the actual dis-
 414 tance because we are considering prefix lengths smaller than the number \tilde{h} of
 415 pivots needed to have the convergence.

416 We remark that the performance of the **Simplex** bounds are poor for *small*
 417 *prefix lengths* mainly because

- 418 • for two objects $o, s \in CandSet(q)$ such that $|\Gamma_{o,q}| < |\Gamma_{s,q}| \ll \tilde{h}$ we may
 419 have $S_{lwb}(o, q) < S_{lwb}(s, q)$ even if $d(o, q) > d(s, q)$;
- 420 • the upper-bound, which is not a metric, particularly fails in approximate
 421 small distances and $S_{upb}(o, o)$ may be much greater than 0.

422 This behaviour of the S_{upb} is somehow observable in the recall values obtained
 423 on the YFFCC100 data: for small l the results of the re-ranking based on the
 424 S_{upb} are better than that of S_{lwb} on the 1M images subset (Fig. 5a), but on 10M
 425 images (Fig. 5b) the curve of S_{upb} never exceeds that of S_{lwb} . The reason is
 426 that the actual distances between the query and the candidate objects are likely
 427 to be smaller when performing the nearest neighbour search on a larger subset
 428 of data. Thus, given that for small l the S_{upb} does not approximate well tiny
 429 distances, the performance of the re-ranking based on the upper-bound drops
 430 when the candidate objects are selected by searching 10M images.

431 It is worth noting that, accordingly to our experimental observations, if we
 432 use the same simplex base (e.g. the one formed by the pivots in the query
 433 permutation prefix) to project all the candidate objects, we achieve re-ranking
 434 scores better than that showed in the Figures above, especially for relatively
 435 small prefix lengths. However, this approach is not directly applicable in the
 436 analysed scenario. In fact, we used inverted files to index the permutations
 437 and store the distances object-pivots. This implies that at query time, for each
 438 candidate object o we had access only to the distances $d(o, p)$ with p appearing
 439 in both the object and query permutation prefixes. Therefore, the set of pivots
 440 employed to build the simplex base changes when considering different candi-
 441 date objects. This means that the “quality” (tightness) of the **Simplex**-based
 442 approximations of the query-object distances is not uniform within the set of
 443 the candidate objects. To overcome this issue, we tested normalised versions of
 444 all the **Simplex** distance bounds by taking into account the number h of pivots
 445 used for projecting the data. In the graphs reported in this paper, we show
 446 only the normalised version of the mean and zenith distance since they were the
 447 ones obtaining the best results. As normalisation factor we used $g(h) = \log(h)$
 448 since we experimentally observed that the relative errors of the Simplex bounds
 449 decrease logarithmically with h (e.g. Figure 6b).

450 The re-rankings based on the normalised versions of the **Simplex** mean and
 451 zenith have practically the same performance on Twitter Glove and SISAP Col-
 452 ors data sets, while on YFCC100M data the $S_{norm.mean}$ shows slightly better
 453 recall values. Moreover, in all the tested cases, the re-rankings using those
 454 **Simplex** measures always improved the permutation-based results (i.e. the
 455 **Perms** baseline). For example, for $n = 4,000$ pivots and $l = 800$, the $recall@10$
 456 is improved from 0.37 to 0.64 on YFCC100M (10M subset). For $n = 4,000$ and
 457 $l = 300$, the recall increases from 0.43 to 0.76 on Twitter-GloVe, while for $l = 80$
 458 and $n = 1,000$ it raises from 0.43 to 0.80 on SISAP Colors. We provided exam-
 459 ples with $l < n$ instead of considering the full-length permutation since when
 460 using inverted files the number of index blocks accessed is proportional to l^2/n
 461 and does not depend on the number of retrieved objects. Moreover, it is worth
 462 to note that the quality of permutation-based results it is not always improved
 463 by considering large prefix lengths. In fact, it often happens that there exists
 464 an optimal prefix length for which we achieve a recall that is better or very
 465 similar to that obtained using the full-length permutations. This phenomenon
 466 is observable in the YFCC100M and the SISAP Colors data set (see Fig. 5
 467 and 4b), where the **Perms** recall line has a plateau or decreases after achieving
 468 a maximum value. Other examples of this phenomenon can be found e.g. in
 469 [18] where it was observed the existence of an optimal prefix length $l < n$ for
 470 some synthetic and real-word data sets. The intuition is that in those cases the
 471 intrinsic complexity of the data set is already well described when permutation
 472 prefixes with length equal to the optimal value are used, therefore increasing
 473 the length of the prefixes may add noisy information instead of improving the
 474 data representation. This phenomenon is not yet completely investigated in
 475 literature, however, we mentioned to clarify why in the SISAP Colors case the
 476 performance is affected by using a large l parameter.

477 Finally, we observe that the cost of the considered re-ranking approaches
 478 depends on the query object since it changes according to the numbers of piv-
 479 ots in the intersections of permutation prefixes of the query and the candidate
 480 objects. If using the algorithm proposed in [10], the cost for building a simplex
 481 base using h pivots is $O(h^3)$ floating point operations (flops), while the cost
 482 for projecting an object is $O(h^2)$ flops. Thus, for k' candidate objects whose
 483 permutation prefixes have on average h_l pivots in common with the query per-
 484 mutation we have a cost of $O(k'(h_l^3 + h_l^2) + h_l^2)$ flops to compute the **Simplex**
 485 bounds. However, the k' simplex bases can be computed in parallel since they
 486 referred to different sets of pivots. Just to provide an example, for $l = 300$ the
 487 time cost for computing all the simplex bases and projecting both the query
 488 and the candidate objects is about 300ms on an Intel i7 3.5 GHz. We also ob-
 489 serve that this cost may be greatly reduced if some of these simplex bases are
 490 pre-computed or partially computed. In facts, if we have a simplex base built
 491 upon the pivot set $\{p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_h}\}$ and we extend it by adding a further pivot the
 492 cost is $O(h^2)$ flops instead of $O(h^3)$ flops needed to build it from scratch. Thus
 493 implementations that exploit hashmaps or prefix trees to dynamically cash the
 494 computed simplex bases would accelerate the response at query time.

Figure 7: YFCC100M, Euclidean distance, $n = 4000$, $l = 800$

495 5.4. Results on large scale

496 To evaluate our techniques on large scale, we perform the k-NN search on
 497 various subsets of YFCC100M. Figure 7a shows the *recall@10* varying the data
 498 set size from 1 to 96 million images. The candidate results to be re-ranked were
 499 selected by using permutation prefixes of length $l = 800$. We observe that the
 500 performance of our techniques with respect to the **Perms** and **re-rank(actual
 501 distance)** baselines is stable when increasing the size of the data set. In par-
 502 ticular, the *relative improvement* in the recall obtained by the **Simplex** mean
 503 and zenith re-rankings with respect to **Perms** results ranges between 70% (at
 504 96M) and 78% (at 8M). Moreover, for large sizes of the data set the relative gap
 505 between our techniques and the re-ranking based on the actual distance slightly
 506 decreases.

507 We also investigate the performance varying the size k' of the candidate set
 508 to be re-ranked (Figure 7b). In this case, the candidate set was selected by
 509 performing a k' -NN search in the permutation space using the Spearman's rho
 510 with location parameter $l = 800$. As expected, the gap between our approaches
 511 and the re-ranking based on the actual distance increases for large sizes of the
 512 candidate set due to the errors in approximating the actual distance by the
 513 **Simplex** measures. In facts, for the considered parameter $l = 800$, on average
 514 we have about 550 pivots in the intersection between the query and the object
 515 permutation prefixes, but for the YFCC100M data set the convergence of the
 516 Simplex bounds is achieved using 4,096 pivots. Thus, the effects of distance
 517 approximation errors becomes more evident when we re-rank larger set of data.
 518 Nevertheless, even when considering $k' = 1,000$ as candidate set size, the im-
 519 provements in the recall of our approach with respect to the **Perms** baseline is
 520 considerable (from 0.35 to 0.59)

(a)

(b)

Figure 8: Examples of 10-NN search results obtained using the permutations without any re-ranking, our Simplex re-ranking technique, and the sequential scan (ground-truth).

Table 2: Examples of disk space in Gigabytes needed by various approaches to index and search the YFCC100M data set using inverted files. The re-ranking based on the Simplex measures requires to store the object-pivot distances within the permutation prefixes. The re-ranking based on the actual distance needs to store the permutation prefixes as well as the original data.

Approach	Disk space (GB)			
	1M deep features		100M deep features	
	$l = 300$	$l = 800$	$l = 300$	$l = 800$
Perms	0.7	1.9	94.3	251.5
Perms, re-rank(actual dist.)	16.0	17.1	1620.5	1777.7
Perms, re-rank(Simplex)	1.8	4.8	206.1	549.5
Perms, re-rank(Simplex) with distances quantized to 8 bits	1.0	2.6	122.2	326.0

521 Finally, in Figure 8, we report some examples of 10-NN results obtained on
522 10M images of YFCC100M using 1) the permutations without any re-ranking,
523 2) our re-ranking approach 3) brute-force (exact search via sequential scan). We
524 considered the case $l = 800$ and we selected examples for which our technique
525 achieved the worse and the best recall@10 over all the 1,000 tested queries,
526 which are 0.1 (Fig. 8a) and 1 (Fig. 8b) respectively. In the first example,
527 it is interesting to note that even if the recall of our technique is very low,
528 from a visual similarity point of view our results are not so worse than the
529 ground-truth images. The second example shows a case in which we achieved
530 the maximum recall (1.0), allowing us to highly improve the recall obtained by
531 the permutation-based search (0.3). Note that in this case, even though the set
532 of our results coincides with the ground-truth set, the ordering of the results is
533 different because for $l = 800$ the Simplex bounds are not converged yet to the
534 actual distance.

535 A demo of the K-NN search results on YFCC100M for various data set
536 sizes (from 1 to 96M) and various re-ranking approaches is available at the link
537 <http://cloudone.isti.cnr.it/rerankingPerms/>.

538 5.5. Results using quantized distances

539 In the experiments analyzed so far, the object-pivot distances used to per-
540 form the re-rankings were indexed within the object permutation prefixes by
541 using inverted files (as discussed in Section 4. The disk space needed by the
542 inverted index can be estimated in general assuming to encode each entry of
543 the posting lists with $\lceil \log_2 |X| \rceil + 32$ bits, where $|X|$ is the size of the data
544 set. This space is largely sufficient to encode both the ID of the object and
545 its distance from the pivot corresponding to the list to which the entry be-
546 longs to. As observed in [14], the positions of the objects can be neglected
547 by ordering the entries of the posting list according to the position of the ob-
548 jects. Therefore, for a fixed l , the size of the inverted index used by our ap-

549 proaches is $l|X|(\lceil \log_2 |X| \rceil + 32)$ bits. For reference we also observe that 1)
 550 the size of the inverted index of the **Perms** approach (i.e. the one that does
 551 not store the distances) is $l|X|(\lceil \log_2 |X| \rceil)$ bits; 2) the search approach relied
 552 on the re-ranking of the permutation-based results according to the actual distance
 553 requires to store both the **Perms** index and the original data set, thus
 554 it needs $l|X|(\lceil \log_2 |X| \rceil) + |X|(\lceil \log_2 |X| \rceil + D * 32)$ bits, if the data objects are
 555 D -dimensional real-valued vectors.

556 For example, the disk space required to index and search 1M deep features
 557 ($D = 4,096$) of YFCC100M using permutation prefixes of length $l = 300$ are
 558 about 1.8 GB for our techniques, 0.7 GB for the **Perms** approach, and 16 GB
 559 for the **Perms**, **re-rank(actual distance)** technique (see also Table 2).

560 To reduce the size of our inverted index, we investigated the idea of com-
 561 pressing the posting lists by storing quantized distances. Since the quantized
 562 distances are then used to compute the Simplex projection of the data objects,
 563 the performance of our re-ranking techniques may degrade due to the quantiza-
 564 tion errors. We investigated this aspect by testing several floating-point quanti-
 565 zation approaches in conjunction with our Simplex-based re-ranking technique.
 566 Specifically, for a value x in a finite range (x_{min}, x_{max}) we tested the following
 567 scalar quantizers.⁵

Uniform quantizer is probably the simplest type of quantizer. It divides the
 interval (x_{min}, x_{max}) into L interval of the same length $Q = (x_{max} -$
 $x_{min})/L$. Each value x is then mapped to the middle value of the interval
 it belong to, i.e.,

$$q_{unif}(x) = x_{min} + Q/2 + Q\lfloor (x - x_{min})/Q \rfloor \quad (7)$$

568 **Nonuniform quantizer** are typically modeled as a cascade of a non-linear
 569 mapping (*compressor*) followed by a uniform quantizer followed by an in-
 570 verse non-linear mapping (*expander*). The non-linear mapping before the
 571 uniform quantization allows us to keep the number of quantization interval
 572 constant while differentiating the size of those intervals to approximate
 573 the input better in certain regions (e.g. regions that have more probability
 574 mass). We considered the following nonuniform quantizers:

μ -law quantizer uses the μ -law mapping as compressor function, which
 is defined as

$$F_{\mu}(x) = V \frac{\log(1 + \mu \frac{|x|}{V})}{\log(1 + \mu)} \text{sign}(x) \quad (8)$$

575 where $V = \max\{|x_{min}|, |x_{max}|\}$, and μ is a compression parameter
 576 (e.g. $\mu = 255$ is used in the North American and Japanese standards
 577 for digital telecommunication signals). The transformed values are

⁵Note that in our case $x_{min} = 0$ since we are considering distance values.

578 then quantized using a uniform quantizer for the trasformed interval.
 579 Thus, the final quantized value associated to x is $q_{unif}(F_\mu(x))$.

To transform a quantized value y back, we use the inverse μ -law:

$$F_\mu^{-1}(y) = \frac{V}{\mu} \left((1 + \mu)^{|y|/V} - 1 \right) \text{sign}(y). \quad (9)$$

580 Since the values close to zero are less compressed than values with
 581 greater absolute values (the quantization intervals increase logarith-
 582 mically), usually the values are mean-centered before the quantiza-
 583 tion.

A-law quantizer uses the A-law compressor, which is defined as

$$F_A(x) = V \text{sign}(x) \begin{cases} \frac{A|x|/V}{1 + \ln(A)} & |x| < V/A \\ \frac{1 + \ln(A|x|/V)}{1 + \ln(A)} & V/A \leq |x| \leq V \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where A is a compression parameter and $V = \max\{|x_{min}|, |x_{max}|\}$.
 The compressed values are then quantized using an uniform quatizer.
 The mapping used as expander is the inverse A-law:

$$F_A^{-1}(y) = \frac{V \text{sign}(y)}{A} \begin{cases} \frac{|y|}{V} (1 + \ln(A)) & |y| < \frac{V}{1 + \ln(A)} \\ \exp\left(\frac{|y|}{V} (1 + \ln(A)) - 1\right) & \frac{V}{1 + \ln(A)} \leq |y| < V \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

584 Also in this case the data are centered before the quantization.

585 The number L of interval we used for each quantizer is $L = 2^{\text{nBits}}$, where
 586 **nBits** are the number of bits used to store each distance. For each approach, we
 587 computed the *Mean Squared Error* (MSE) on a sample set of data. The MSE is
 588 a frequently used to evaluate how close are the (reconstructed) quantized values
 589 x' to the original values x , and it is defined as $\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (x_i - x'_i)^2$, where m is
 590 the number of samples.

591 For the μ -law and A-law quantizer, we select the optimal μ and A param-
 592 eters as the ones providing us the lowest MSE over a sample set of object-pivots
 593 distances. We then evaluate the recall obtained by re-ranking the permutation-
 594 based candidate set according to the Simplex bounds computed using the quan-
 595 tized distances. Table 3 shows comparative results on 1M subset of YFCC100M
 596 using a prefix length of $l = 800$ and **nBits** = 8.

597 As expected the uniform quantizer has really poor results since the distri-
 598 bution of the distances is not uniform. The tested nonuniform quantizers have
 599 results similar to each other. We decided to use the μ -law quantizer since it
 600 showed slightly better results.

601 We then thoroughly tested the performance of our technique by varying
 602 the data set, the permutation prefix length l , and the number of bits used to

Table 3: Results of various quantization approaches (YFCC100M data set). The quantizers are applied to the distances of the data objects to their l nearest pivots, i.e. the distances store in the posting lists. The reported results were obtained using the `Perms, re-rank($S_{norm.mean}$)` approach, distance quantized to 8 bits, and permutation prefixes of length $l = 800$.

Quantizer	Compressor parameter	MSE	recall@10
Uniform		3.24E-03	0.228
μ -law	$\mu = 48$	2.64E-07	0.698
A-law	$A = 3$	1.04E-06	0.696
No quantization		0	0.698

603 store each object-pivot distance. Figures 9, 10, and 11 illustrate the results on
604 YFCCC100M, SISAP Colors, and Twitter GloVe, respectively. For the sake
605 of simplicity, we show results obtained using a fixed parameter μ for all tested
606 permutation prefix lengths. This parameter was selected as the one minimising
607 the MSE error in approximating the distances of the objects to all the n pivots.
608 In facts, we observe that results obtained in this way are practically equivalent
609 to that obtained by estimating an optimal parameter μ for each different choice
610 of the parameter l .

611 On YFCC100M (Euclidean distance) and SISAP Colors (Jensen-Shannon
612 distance), we were able to satisfactorily preserve the quality of the re-ranked
613 results when using at least 8 bits to store each distance. However, we observed
614 a huge degradation when using fewer bits. For example, the re-ranked results
615 became worse than the permutation-results when we use less than 5 bits. The
616 problem is that the quantized object-pivot distances are then used to compute
617 the Simplex projection of the object, so the quantization errors propagate in the
618 Simplex-based estimation of the query-object distance. The effect of this error
619 propagation is more evident in Twitter Glove data (cosine distance), where the
620 results obtained for $l \geq 300$ is highly degraded using quantized distances. On
621 this data set, we needed about 14 bits to preserve the quality of the re-ranked
622 results even though the MSE errors related to distances quantized using fewer
623 bits were in line with that obtained in the other tested data sets.

624 6. Conclusions

625 In this article, we presented an approach that exploit a pivot-based local em-
626 bedding to refine a set of candidate results of a similarity query. The analysed
627 case is refining of a set of approximate nearest neighbour results retrieved using
628 a permutation-based search system. However, our approach can be generalized
629 to other types of approximate search provided that they are based on the use of
630 anchor objects (pivots) from which we pre-calculate the distances for other pur-
631 poses. For example, some data structures use inverted indices, as the inverted
632 multi-index [35], in which objects belonging to a Voronoi cell are inserted in a

(a) Probability distribution of the distances between the data objects and the n pivots

(b) Mean Squared Error for the μ -law quantization varying μ

(c) $Recall@10$ varying the permutation prefix length l ($\mu = 57$)

Figure 9: *YFCC100M* (1M), Euclidean distance, $n = 4,000$ pivots

(a) Probability distribution of the distances between the data objects and the n pivots

(b) Mean Squared Error for the μ -law quantization varying μ

(c) Recall@10 varying the permutation prefix length l ($\mu = 3$)

Figure 10: SISAP colors, Jensen-Shannon distance, $n = 1,000$

(a) Probability distribution of the distances between the data objects and the n pivots

(b) Mean Squared Error for the μ -law quantization varying μ

(c) $Recall@10$ varying the permutation prefix length l ($\mu = 40$)

Figure 11: *Twitter Glove*, *Cosine distance*, $n = 4,000$

633 posting list associated with the centroid of the cell from which we calculated
634 the distance. Other indexes that can benefit from our approach are those based
635 on permutation prefix trees, like PP-Index [2] and PPP-Index [16].

636 The core idea of the proposed technique is using the distances between an
637 object and a set of pivots (pre-computed at indexing time) to embed the data ob-
638 jects in a metric space where it is possible to compute upper- and lower-bounds
639 for the actual distance. Dissimilarity functions defined upon those bounds are
640 then adopted for re-ranking the candidate objects. The main advantage is that
641 the proposed approach do not need to access the original data as done, instead,
642 by the most commonly used refining technique that relies on computing the
643 actual distances between the query and each candidate object.

644 We analysed the refining based on two data embeddings, namely the Piv-
645 oted embedding and the nSimplex projection, and several dissimilarity func-
646 tions derived by these space transformations. The refining approaches us-
647 ing the nSimplex projection resulted to be particularly effective for refining
648 permutation-based results. For example, using the refining according to the
649 nSimplex normalised mean function we were able to almost double the preci-
650 sion the permutation-based results even on a data set of about 100 million of
651 objects.

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